

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Phenylacetaldehyde by Chromic Acid

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The kinetics of the oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde by chromic acid has been studied. The reaction is of first order with respect to each of the acid chromate ion, HCrO_4^- , and the aldehyde. The rate is proportional to the square of hydrogen ion concentration. The enolisation rate is also measured. The activation parameters for the oxidation and enolisation reactions have been evaluated. The enolisation is much slower than the oxidation. A mechanism involving an attack on the keto-form of the aldehyde is proposed.

Previously we showed that aliphatic aldehydes are oxidised via their keto-form¹. Several studies on the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes by Cr(VI) are available^{2,3}, but there seems to be no report on the oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde. In the present investigation the role of enolisation in the oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde is examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : Phenylacetaldehyde was purified by the usual methods. Perchloric acid (60%, E.Merck) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to adjust ionic strength. Acetic acid (B.D.H., AnalaR) was distilled over chromic oxide before use. All other chemicals used were chemically pure.

All other experimental procedures have been described earlier¹.

RESULTS

Product Analysis : Phenylacetic acid is the main product of the oxidation. Its estimation shows that for one mole of Cr(VI) consumed nearly 1.5 mole of phenylacetic acid is produced. The overall reaction may be written as :

Rate Laws : When the concentration of the aldehyde is in excess, the rate of disappearance of Cr(VI) follows first rate laws. However, the rate constants decrease with increase in the initial concentration of Cr(VI). The reaction shows characteristics of first order dependence on acid chromate ions, HCrO_4^- . The reaction is of first order with respect to the aldehyde also. At constant ionic strength, the oxidation rate is proportional to the square of hydrogen ion concentration. Increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent mixture (20–80%) increases the oxidation rate sharply ($k_1 = 9.5-90 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}^{-1}$).

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Effect of Temperature : The reaction was studied at temperatures between 25°–40° (Table 1) and activation parameters evaluated. The specific rate constant, k , is obtained from the relation $k = k_1[\text{Aldehyde}][\text{H}^+]^2$.

Rate of Enolisation. Rate of bromination of the aldehyde is of first order with respect to each of the organic substrate and hydrogen ions but of zero to bromine. Table 2 records the bromination rate and activation parameters.

DISCUSSION

A comparison of data of Tables 1 and 2 shows that the oxidation is much faster than enolisation. Moreover, the activation energy is lower in the chromic acid oxidation than in enolisation. On both these grounds we are forced to conclude that enolisation cannot be involved in the oxidation.

TABLE 1

Oxidation of Phenylacetaldehyde by chromic acid

Solvent : 20% Acetic acid-80% (water (v/v))

Temp. K	$k(1^3\text{mol}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1})$	ΔH^* kcal/mole	ΔS^* e.u.
298	0.170	10.0 ± 0.5	-29 ± 1.5
303	0.260		
308	0.350		$\Delta F^* 298_K$
313	0.448		18.6 ± 1.0 kcal/mole
318	0.568		

TABLE 2

Enolisation rate

Solvent : 20% Acetic acid—80% water.

Temp. K	$10^4 k_2$ $1 \text{ mol}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$	ΔH^* kcal/mol	ΔS^* e.u.	ΔF^*_{298K} kcal/mol
298	1.5			
303	2.2	14.2 ± 0.7	-30 ± 2	26.0 ± 1.5
308	3.1			
313	4.6			
318	6.5			

The chromic acid oxidation of alcohols⁴ and aldehydes¹ involve the initial formation of the chromate ester or its conjugate acid. Such an intermediate is most likely in the oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde also.

Wiberg and Mill² and Graham and Westheimer³ proposed that the oxidation of aromatic aldehydes involve transfer of a proton to the oxidant. However, chromic acid oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes show a reaction constant $\rho^* = -1.05$ pointing to an electron deficient

carbon centre in the transition state¹. This supports the hydride transfer mechanism proposed earlier by Rocek⁵. Thus the oxidation of phenylacetaldehyde is best represented as involving a hydride ion transfer.

REFERENCES,

1. C. Goswami and K. K. Banerji, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1970, **43**, 2643; *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 5039; *E. Naturforsch.*, 1971, **26B**, 383.
2. K. B. Wiberg and T. Mill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3022.
3. G. T. E. Graham and F. H. Westheimer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3030.
4. K. B. Wiberg and H. Schafer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 927, 933.
5. J. Rocek, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1959, No. 5, 1.

